

A BRIEF LIFE JOURNEY OF A MULTIDISCIPLINARY STUDENT OF THE OPEN EDUCATION SYSTEM OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE

By

Prof. Deepak Ganpatrao Dongare

Ex. Coordinator

District Office Y.C.M. Open University, Latur.

LATUR 413 512(MAH)

Mobile No. 9422940553

E-Mail ID : deepakdongare54@gmail.com

PREFACE

Prof. Vaijnath R. Dadge Librarian, was a Gold Medalist Library Icon and best Information Officer at Shiv Chatraparti Shikshan Sanstha's Rajarshi Shahu Mahavidyalaya, Latur. From 1975 I was connected with the Rajarshi Shahu College. Before that my older sister Prabhavati Dongare Madam from the beginning was an assistant Hindi Language Teacher at the Yashwant Vidyalaya of the same Shikshan Sanstha and she got the Head Mistress seat before the division of Yashwant Vidyalaya into another school for girls named Jijamata Kannya School and carried for 19 years services as the Head Mistress there uptill her retirement. She devoted her total life for the education of boys and girls in all, I salute her with the gratitude and also to be my Godfather.

GRASPING OF THE CURRIER

I started my life journey at the age of 16, the year 1970 in Latur where I borned, schooled at Puranmal Lahoti Pathshala, then Shri Marwadi Rajasthan Vidyalaya and @ the Commerce Collge of Dayanand Education Society Latur. The breakful and continued education as the generations changes I mould myself at every nook and corner to cope up with drastic changes occurred to our batch. All that glittering is not gold, like that the forthcoming professions in my life changing according to need of people and the society. We were attracted by the professions of 1.Barristers 2.Stenographers 3.Chartered accountants 4,Foreign Languages 5.Govt.Officials 6.Banking Field 7.MPSC 8.UPSC 9.MBA 10.Doctors 11.Engineers 12.College Professors, etc.

BASIC EDUCATION: LEARNING

So, I had selected for me the Stenography English Trade at I.T.I. Latur in 1973-74 batch and successfully completed. At RSML I joined as a steno typist and continued for only Four Months services. In 1980 I joined to Latur Industrial Estate Cooperative Society @ Udyog Bhavan upto 1984. Earlier of 1980 I was struggling for my B.Com. Degree with English Medium.

FAMILY LIFE & TEACHING

Here my thirst of teaching to students takes place and I turn to Typewriting & Shorthand Commercial Institute of my own Deep Commercial Institute, Here I feel satisfied as I was stamped by Maharashtra Government as the Principal of Government recognized institution. After registration with the Mahaarashtra Government in 1986 I had a turningpoint for my bachelor life, and got married with my life partner Sow. Lalita Dongare (Shinde). I feel very lucky when I found as per my choice the learned partner preferred. She was matriculated and also learned typing. She joined her full education, double PG in the subjects History and Library Science, a Librarian with Homeopathy Medical College, Latur for two yers and secondly she joined the Dental College of MIT at Latur upto Tweleve years and she developed the Dental Library Books upto Rupees Three Crores fullfledged the Library Stock. Here the SLEEM software installed for automation of this Library.

I was landless and upto 1970 there was no own home of ours. Here in Latur my father purchased a piece of land at prime location and expired. He honoured for his 27 Years Long Services with the Ahsoka Trophy Award by the Brooke Bond Tea Company where he served in Latur.

OWN INSTITUE & TEACHING

The years1984 to 1994 this decade was of Deep Commercial Institute. Here the students of Typing & Shorthand struggled for real Professional and Practical education and set in their life positively. In their life they got the importance of time duration and their zeal to utilize for, who devoted for their study and practices they are now on a key posts here or there. At the same time my life partner who has completed her matriculation got married with me. She also involve to hold the line of education with me. My Deep commercial Institute and Manual Xerox Centre conducted throughout years 1986 to 1993 with full swing. Here in 1993 the Natural calamity occurred this is the Earthquake at Latur.

YCM OPEN UNIVERSITY & SOCIAL ACTIVITIES

In the 1994 I forced to windup my Institute due to Earthquake Impact and I joined the rehabilitation programme of YCMOU for the Latur and Osmanabad District. The YCMOU Nashik alongwith the Oxfam International N.G.O., tieup for three years and closed at the end of 1996. Here I was appointed as an Assistant Project Officer. This rpogramme converted into a District Office of YCMOU for Latur District in 1998 that is Pt. Gopbandhu Das Lokshikshan Kendra, Latur.

COLLEGE UG & PG LEVEL TEACHING

Simultaneously in year 1995 I offered my teaching services to our Rajarshi Shahu College for UG B.Com. students learning English Shorthand & Typewriting UGC Scheme executed for professional study courses for Five Year Programme, having all fascilities with Class Rooms,

Typewriters & OHP, etc. In the mean time I completed B.Lib.& I.Sc. with my bride Mrs. Lalita and that was motivated by the Students Services @ YCMOU Nashik, the classes for B.Lib.& I.Sc. conducted in my office. The facility of M.Lib. & I.Sc. at Rajarshi Shahu College was available in continuing education with the Virtual Classroom at P.G. Level. Prof. Dadge Sir was the Coordinator & Chief-in-Charge of the Study Centre for M.Lib. & I.Sc. The next step was to join the team of Librarians who were already experienced as the Library Staff and had the knowledge of the Library Science. Upto 2012 my retirement age I counselled the students of the M.Lib.& I.Sc.

DUTIES AND OBLIGATIONS

Education of P.G. was hurdle race for me, side by side with my all duties vested with the District Office all the roles in office should play as One Act Play. That was the period of Land Line Phones and the technology of Computer & Communication taking place with manual office routine. The EDUSAT satellite launched for better Communication and Online Education. Here in the District Office the direct Satellite Communication System installed and same for the Rajarshi Shahu College too. The conferences and meet conducted with two way Audio-Visual Systems. This facility for the colleges in all over the Maharashtra and connected to YCMOU Nashik Head Office, the Virtual Classes were conducted.

TECHNOLOGY TREND : LEARNING & TEACHING

The Time Management is essential for all sort of targets. The Short, Medium and Long Term targets can be achieved with full satisfaction. All sorts of obligations allotted to me were fulfilled at all costs and by all means and the result oriented. In the year 2010 myself honored for research paper in which futuristic statements were made, that in future there the Library Data collection of all sorts i.e. Print, Optical, Magnetic, Audio Video streaming throughout the world will be available with you and in your pockets too. The cause and reason behind this was the increasing storage capacity of data devices and broadband dissemination of all above information with immense speed and just in time. Science and Technology advanced to nano perceptions, the use of Wired and Wireless Communication Technology changed all the scenario of the world towards advancements in all spheres of human life. Bits to bytes and to K.B., M.B., G.B., T.B. and so on. The Generation changed to 2G to 3,4,5,6th Generations. The Limitations of Libraries came into endless Information and Data Collection of varied fields and streams of knowledge.

THE LIBRARY FOUNDATION

Prof. V.R.Dadge Library Foundation was established after the immense efforts by Prof. V.N. Mishra the Librarian @ Ausa College Dist. Latur. The aim of the foundation covers the Towns & District to the State Level. "The Grantha Tula", the weighing the person & his personality of V.R.Dadge Sir. Since last Three Years this Library Foundation consistently arranging the

National Library Conferences at Latur, Udgir and now at Ambad Dist. Jalna, the Sister University the Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University Sambhajinagar.

Now the extra curricular activities are conducted at the organization level the foundation is advancing towards the utmost knowledge conservation with fevicol bond of the colleges and libraries/information centres. As the journey of foundation is advancing with the help of the online Zoom Meetings, Digital Journals and the Website of PVRDL Foundation, all the activities motivates to future prospects.

ALL IN ONE

My Open University Education at RSML and Usha Computer Centre was a landmark and the turning point for my further education. I have completed my Diploma in Computer Operation and also Masters Degree in Library and Information Science. Due to post graduation like a multidisciplinary subject alongwith C.D.s, and distance education, my view enhanced upto level of depth teaching and due to research papers the core education level was perfected. Hereafter the obligation and duties in education line, well acquainted with the knowledge system and changing information with a specific line or stream of knowledge and education. The YCMOU gave me the opportunity for the profeciency in Library & Information Science. I served the University at my utmost upto year 2012, though I played mono act at the District Office as a single man army in University's own District Study Centre as the Pilot Project in Maharashtra.

TOWARDS TOURISM AND FOREIGN CULTURE

Here all these abilities and qualities of mine and education i.e. Four Wheeler Driving, International driving Permit supports me in the Euro Zone for travelling by Car with ease @ the 160 Km/h the normal speed there on the Four Lanes Inter State Roads from Brussels to Munich. The driving with Limitles speed can be enjoyed with balancing of your vehicle with easy and smooth driving possible here in Euro Zone, particularly on the German Roads. Everyone can study the foreign countries which are advanced. 1600 Kms journey by the BMW Car driving each side 800 Kms with a gap of four days, which is unfurgaottable journey. In the Germany there my nephew is residing since 20 years in Munich, where we visit and enjoyed four days residence. Thrill of driving and confidence takes me in a different world, my Life Partner, my younger Son residing at Brussels and his Spouse was the company in this journey was remarkable.

In foreign country we have to enter with all preparations. The first of all you have to got the preliminary knowledge of the foreign languages preferably English, and secondly their local language where we are going, the weather of that region, the locality, the conversation skills though is not with you the Genaral Knowledge is but essential. You should be able to Cycling, Two Wheeler riding and next to that the Four Wheeler Driving Licence and IDP (International Driving Permit) is a must. You should have to insert a sim card of that region or country in your mobile phone and that will good and better with the payments fascility in it. Your wearings the cloths should be inclusive of all respects formal and informal. If you can enjoy the Nature's

closeness then it will be fruitful for you. Before departing, the Language of that particular country should studied at the primary level, for this you can appear for the certificate course of the same and complete with that respect. The Duolingo Mobile App can be tried. You should carry the required or regular medicines from your family doctor for general seekness and frequently used so.

Paper Setter, Examiner, Moderator, Committee Chairman with the SRTMU Nanded for Shorthand/Stenography at the B.Com. level.

Invigilator, external examiner to AUSA college, COCSIT College @ Latur for B.A., B.Com., MBA and also implemented the Technical exams of the University @ Kallam, Washi Dist Osmanabad.

Presented paper and attended Two Days National Conference at Gunjoti - Shrikrishna Mahavidyalaya and honoured for article on Wired and wireless Technology in year 2010 awarded with the Parker Pen.

Foreign Language Learning: In Latur ITI the Cognate English subject for Stenography English Trade, studied from the Parts of Speech upto Figures of speech and acquainted with the Formation of words, Sentence Pattern and culture of England in 700 common words book studied. Due to English Language the Russian Language @ RSML and the Dutch Lnaguage with the help of Duolingo Software App where I stood in Top Three in the Gold League with Russian Students and others.

Technical Skills: Can assemble Bicycle, Musical Horn Installation, the gadget fo water level indicator buzzer alarm, Electric Cycles of 36 volts circuit, and the technical knowhow of Machines and Tools.

PAPERS PRESENTED IN THE NATIONAL CONFERENCES :

- 1) Language learning skill with Advanced Technology, parallel to Degree Education. “2024. “
- 2) Advances of Information Technology with regards to Digital Libraries” 2010. ”

BFIEF BIOGRAPHY OF AUTHOR :

Dongare Deepak was the Coordinator at Yashwantrao Chavan Maharashtra Open University's District Office named as Pt. Gopbandhu Das Lokshikshan Kendra, Latur. Simultaneously worked as Lecturer to B.Lib. & I.Sc. and Counsellor to M.Lib. & I.Sc. programmes of YCMOU, at Rajarshi Shahu College, Latur. Holds B.Com., M.Lib & I. Sc., D.C.O., Stenography (English). He had Eighteen Years of Teaching Experience.